

Stochastic Mechanics Redux

Mark Davidson¹

¹*Independent Physicist, Spectel Research Co., Palo Alto, CA, USA**

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Edward Nelson’s stochastic mechanics reproduces the single-time probability densities of quantum mechanics but fails to reproduce multi-time correlations. This failure leads to a violation of *dynamical separability*: for two non-interacting but entangled systems, the autocorrelation of a particle in one system depends on parameters of the distant, non-interacting system. Nelson considered this fatal. We show that this deficiency is not inherent to stochastic mechanics but rather to the choice of a real diffusion constant. By selecting the *imaginary* diffusion constant $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$, the stochastic process evolves in complex space, and the associated operator algebra becomes isomorphic to the Heisenberg algebra. Using analytic continuation of multi-time expectations from real to complex ν , we prove that for this choice the stochastic multi-time correlations exactly equal the quantum mechanical ones. Consequently, dynamical separability is restored. We explicitly verify this in Nelson’s original counterexample—a free particle entangled with a harmonic oscillator—and demonstrate that the complex stochastic autocorrelation matches the quantum mechanical result and is independent of the distant oscillator’s dynamics. We also discuss speculative connections to chaotic dynamics, the Lorentz-Dirac equation and radiation reaction, Bell’s theorem, and non-Markovian stochastic models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stochastic mechanics (SM) [1–6] provides a diffusion process whose probability density coincides with $|\psi(x, t)|^2$ of the Schrödinger equation. Despite this success, Nelson abandoned the theory because of a violation of *dynamical separability* [7]: for two spatially separated, non-interacting systems prepared in an entangled state, the multi-time autocorrelation of a

* mdavid@spectelresearch.com

particle in the first system depends on the Hamiltonian of the *second* system. This effect is absent in standard quantum mechanics and, Nelson argued, constitutes a fatal nonlocality.

Several authors proposed salvaging SM by incorporating wavefunction collapse [8–10], but Nelson remained unconvinced. Here we take a different route: we generalize the diffusion constant. In *generalized stochastic mechanics* (GSM) [11, 12], the diffusion constant ν can be any complex number; all choices yield the same Born distribution on the real axis. The conventional choice $\nu = \hbar/2m$ is not unique. The theory of stochastic mechanics with an imaginary diffusion constant has been further developed and analyzed by Rosenbrock [13–15], Wang [16, 17], Kuipers [18], and Yang [19]. Rosenbrock’s work is particularly significant because he showed that for $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$, the Born rule applies at the *crossing points* where the complex trajectory intersects the real axis, providing a physical interpretation of quantum phenomena such as interference and tunneling (see Appendix B).

We show that the specific choice $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ — corresponding to diffusion in *complex* space — completely resolves Nelson’s dilemma. For this value the stochastic operator algebra becomes the Heisenberg algebra, and by analytic continuation of multi-time expectations we prove that the stochastic correlations equal the quantum ones. Consequently dynamical separability is restored. We illustrate this with Nelson’s original counterexample.

II. NELSON’S DYNAMICAL SEPARABILITY PROBLEM

Consider two independent quantum systems with Hamiltonians H_1 on \mathcal{H}_1 and H_2 on \mathcal{H}_2 . The composite Hilbert space is $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$ with

$$H = H_1 \otimes \mathbb{I} + \mathbb{I} \otimes H_2. \quad (1)$$

For any observable A_1 acting on \mathcal{H}_1 alone, the Heisenberg evolution is

$$A_1(t) \otimes \mathbb{I} = e^{iHt/\hbar}(A_1 \otimes \mathbb{I})e^{-iHt/\hbar} = e^{iH_1t/\hbar}A_1e^{-iH_1t/\hbar} \otimes \mathbb{I}. \quad (2)$$

Hence for any (possibly entangled) state $|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{H}$, the multi-time correlation

$$\langle \Psi | A_1(t_1) \cdots A_1(t_n) \otimes \mathbb{I} | \Psi \rangle$$

depends only on H_1 and the initial state, not on H_2 . This is *dynamical separability*.

Nelson [7] exhibited a counterexample in real SM. Take two one-dimensional particles with

$$H_1 = -\frac{d^2}{dx_1^2}, \quad H_2 = -\frac{d^2}{dx_2^2} + \frac{\omega^2 x_2^2}{2}, \quad (3)$$

so particle 1 is free and particle 2 is a harmonic oscillator of frequency ω . They do not interact. In these units $m = 1$ and $\hbar = \sqrt{2}$, hence Nelson's diffusion constant is $\nu_N = \hbar/(2m) = 1/\sqrt{2}$. The initial state is the entangled Gaussian

$$\Psi(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{4}(x_1^2 - 2x_1x_2 + 2x_2^2)\right], \quad (4)$$

which has covariance matrix

$$\langle x_i x_j \rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

John Lafferty (personal communication, cited in [7]) computed the position autocorrelation of the free particle using symbolic manipulation. Nelson reports the following result.¹

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\xi_1(t)\xi_1(0)] &= 2 - \frac{1}{2}t + \frac{1}{4}t - \frac{1}{12}t^3 - \frac{5}{96}t^4 \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{13}{192} - \frac{\omega^2}{80}\right)t^5 + O(t^6). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The ω^2 term shows that the distant oscillator influences the autocorrelation of particle 1, in violation of dynamical separability.

In sharp contrast, the quantum autocorrelation $\langle x_1(t)x_1(0) \rangle$ for this state is independent of ω . For a free particle $x_1(t) = x_1 + p_1 t$ (with $m = 1$). Because the wave function (4) is real, one finds $\langle p_1 x_1 \rangle = -i\hbar/2 = -i/\sqrt{2}$, hence

$$\langle x_1(t)x_1(0) \rangle = \langle x_1^2 \rangle + t\langle p_1 x_1 \rangle = 2 - it/\sqrt{2}, \quad (7)$$

which contains no ω dependence. This discrepancy led Nelson to reject real SM.

III. GENERALIZED STOCHASTIC MECHANICS

GSM [11, 12] introduces a one-parameter family of diffusions with diffusion constant

$$\nu(z) = z \frac{\hbar}{2m}, \quad (8)$$

¹ The presence of two distinct linear terms is unusual; it may be a typographical error, and the intended expression is likely $-\frac{1}{2}t + \frac{1}{4}t^2$. However the essential feature—the appearance of ω^2 at $O(t^5)$ —is unambiguous.

where z is a non-zero complex number. The forward SDE is

$$d\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}(t), t; z) dt + \sqrt{2\nu(z)} d\mathbf{w}(t), \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{w}(t)$ a standard Wiener process in \mathbb{R}^n . The drift is chosen so that the probability density $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = |\psi(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2$ satisfies the same Fokker-Planck equation as in Nelson's theory. Writing $\psi = e^{R+iS_Q}$, one has

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t; z) = 2\nu(z)\nabla\left(R(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{1}{z}S_Q(\mathbf{x}, t)\right). \quad (10)$$

For real $z > 0$ the diffusion takes place in real space; for complex z it drives the process into \mathbb{C}^n .

The special value $z = -i$ gives

$$\nu_c := \nu(-i) = -i\frac{\hbar}{2m}. \quad (11)$$

Substituting $z = -i$ into (10) yields

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\nabla(R + iS_Q) = \frac{\hbar}{m}\nabla(S_Q - iR). \quad (12)$$

Analytically continuing ψ to complex coordinates $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{x} + i\mathbf{y}$, we obtain the compact form

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{z}, t) = -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\nabla_{\mathbf{z}} \ln \psi(\mathbf{z}, t), \quad (13)$$

and the SDE becomes

$$d\mathbf{z}(t) = -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\nabla_{\mathbf{z}} \ln \psi(\mathbf{z}(t), t) dt + \sqrt{-i\frac{\hbar}{m}} d\mathbf{w}(t). \quad (14)$$

Rosenbrock [13, 14] analyzed this complex diffusion in detail, showing that by introducing the rotated coordinates $X = x+y$ and $Y = x-y$, the X component evolves deterministically. More importantly, he demonstrated that the Born rule applies at the *crossing points* where the trajectory intersects the real axis ($y = 0$), providing a physical interpretation of quantum phenomena such as interference and tunneling. This analysis is summarized in Appendix B.

IV. OPERATOR ALGEBRA FROM THE STOCHASTIC PROCESS

Following [20–22], we construct a non-commuting operator algebra directly from the stochastic process. Fix a time s and define the weighted Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_s = L^2(\mathbb{R}^n, \rho(\mathbf{x}, s)d^n\mathbf{x})$ with inner product

$$(f, g)_s = \mathbb{E}[f^*(\mathbf{x}(s), s)g(\mathbf{x}(s), s)] = \int f^*(\mathbf{x}, s)g(\mathbf{x}, s)\rho(\mathbf{x}, s)d^n\mathbf{x}. \quad (15)$$

The position operator $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ acts as multiplication by \mathbf{x} . The velocity operator $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ acting on \mathcal{H}_s is defined by

$$(\hat{\mathbf{v}}f)(\mathbf{x}, s) = \lim_{t \downarrow s} \lim_{u \downarrow s} \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}(u)f(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \mid \mathbf{x}(s) = \mathbf{x}]. \quad (16)$$

Evaluating this limit gives

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, s) + 2\nu \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}. \quad (17)$$

A straightforward computation yields the commutator

$$[\hat{v}_i, \hat{x}_j] = 2\nu \delta_{ij}. \quad (18)$$

Defining momentum $\hat{p}_i = m\hat{v}_i$, we have

$$[\hat{p}_i, \hat{x}_j] = 2m\nu \delta_{ij}. \quad (19)$$

To obtain the Heisenberg relation $[\hat{p}_i, \hat{x}_j] = -i\hbar \delta_{ij}$ we need $2m\nu = -i\hbar$, i.e. $\nu = -i\hbar/(2m)$. Thus ν_c is exactly the value that reproduces the canonical commutation relations. An imaginary diffusion constant was already proposed by Fürth in 1933 [23, 24], providing a segue to the later works of Fényes and Nelson.

A. Connecting to the standard quantum mechanical representation

The weighted Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_s is convenient for constructing operators from the stochastic process, but to relate to conventional quantum mechanics we need to map it to the standard $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n, d^n \mathbf{x})$ space. A natural unitary map is given by multiplication by the wave function itself:

$$W_s : \mathcal{H}_s \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{R}^n), \quad (W_s f)(\mathbf{x}) = \psi(\mathbf{x}, s) f(\mathbf{x}, s), \quad (20)$$

where $\psi(\mathbf{x}, s) = e^{R(\mathbf{x}, s) + iS_Q(\mathbf{x}, s)}$. This map is unitary because

$$\langle W_s f | W_s g \rangle_{L^2} = \int \psi^*(\mathbf{x}, s) f^*(\mathbf{x}, s) \psi(\mathbf{x}, s) g(\mathbf{x}, s) d^n \mathbf{x} = \int e^{2R(\mathbf{x}, s)} f^* g d^n \mathbf{x} = (f, g)_s.$$

Its inverse is $(W_s^{-1} \phi)(\mathbf{x}, s) = \psi(\mathbf{x}, s)^{-1} \phi(\mathbf{x}) = e^{-R(\mathbf{x}, s) - iS_Q(\mathbf{x}, s)} \phi(\mathbf{x})$.

Under this transformation, the position operator \hat{x}_i (multiplication by x_i) retains its standard form because $W_s \hat{x}_i W_s^{-1}$ simply multiplies by x_i .

Now consider the velocity operator $\hat{v}_i = b_i(\mathbf{x}, s) + 2\nu\partial_i$ acting in \mathcal{H}_s . Its image under W_s is

$$\begin{aligned} (W_s \hat{v}_i W_s^{-1} \phi)(\mathbf{x}) &= \psi(\mathbf{x}, s) (b_i(\mathbf{x}, s) + 2\nu\partial_i) (\psi(\mathbf{x}, s)^{-1} \phi(\mathbf{x})) \\ &= b_i(\mathbf{x}, s) \phi(\mathbf{x}) + 2\nu\psi(\mathbf{x}, s) \partial_i (\psi(\mathbf{x}, s)^{-1} \phi(\mathbf{x})). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The derivative term expands as

$$\partial_i(\psi^{-1}\phi) = -\psi^{-2}(\partial_i\psi)\phi + \psi^{-1}\partial_i\phi = -\psi^{-1}(\partial_i \ln \psi)\phi + \psi^{-1}\partial_i\phi.$$

Thus,

$$\psi\partial_i(\psi^{-1}\phi) = -(\partial_i \ln \psi)\phi + \partial_i\phi.$$

Substituting into (21) gives

$$(W_s \hat{v}_i W_s^{-1} \phi)(\mathbf{x}) = (b_i(\mathbf{x}, s) - 2\nu\partial_i \ln \psi(\mathbf{x}, s) + 2\nu\partial_i) \phi(\mathbf{x}). \quad (22)$$

Now recall that for the specific diffusion constant $\nu_c = -i\hbar/2m$, the drift takes the form (13): $b_i = -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\partial_i \ln \psi$. Moreover, $\partial_i \ln \psi = \partial_i R + i\partial_i S_Q$. Substituting these into (22) with $\nu = \nu_c$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} W_s \hat{v}_i W_s^{-1} &= -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\partial_i \ln \psi + i\frac{\hbar}{m}\partial_i \ln \psi - i\frac{\hbar}{m}\partial_i \\ &= -i\frac{\hbar}{m}\partial_i. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Thus the transformed velocity operator is exactly the standard quantum mechanical velocity operator $\hat{p}_i/m = -i\hbar\partial_i/m$. Consequently, the momentum operator in the standard representation becomes $\hat{p}_i = m\hat{v}_i = -i\hbar\partial_i$, and the canonical commutation relation $[\hat{x}_i, \hat{p}_j] = i\hbar\delta_{ij}$ is recovered.

This shows that after analytic continuation to $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$, the stochastic process yields a representation of the Heisenberg algebra identical to that of ordinary quantum mechanics. The unitary map W_s depends on the wave function, reflecting the fact that the construction is state-dependent, but the resulting operators are the familiar ones acting on $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$.

B. Acceleration and Ehrenfest theorem

Defining the acceleration operator via the second derivative of the conditional expectation, one obtains the generalized Ehrenfest relation that is derived in the next section and was

earlier derived in [20–22].

$$m\hat{\mathbf{a}} = -\nabla V(\mathbf{x}) + \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} + 2m\nu^2\right)\nabla\left(\frac{\Delta\sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}}\right). \quad (24)$$

For $\nu = \pm i\hbar/2m$ the curvature term vanishes, yielding the exact Heisenberg equation $m\ddot{\hat{\mathbf{x}}} = -\nabla V(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$. Thus the operator dynamics coincide with quantum mechanics.

C. Higher derivatives and the recursion formula

We can generalize the construction above to define higher derivative operators. For any positive integer m , define

$$\hat{x}_m f(x, s) \equiv \lim_{t \downarrow u} \lim_{u \downarrow s} \frac{\partial^m}{\partial u^m} E(x(u)f(x(t), t)|x(s) = x). \quad (25)$$

These operators satisfy a fundamental recursion relation that reveals their algebraic structure. To derive this recursion, we begin by expressing the conditional expectation in (25) as an iterated integral:

$$E(x(u)f(x(t), t)|x(s) = x) = \int dx_u \int dx_t x_u P(x_u, u|x, s) f(x_t, t) P(x_t, t|x_u, u).$$

Taking the time derivative with respect to u and using the backward Kolmogorov equation for the transition probability $P(x_u, u|x, s)$, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \int dx_u x_u P(x_u, u|x, s) = \mathcal{L}_u \int dx_u x_u P(x_u, u|x, s),$$

where $\mathcal{L}_u = b(x, u)\nabla_x + \nu\nabla_x^2$ is the backward generator of the diffusion process. Applying this repeatedly and using the Markov property leads to the following recursion formula [21]:

$$\hat{x}_{m+1} = [\mathcal{L}_s, \hat{x}_m] + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \hat{x}_m. \quad (26)$$

Derivation of the recursion formula: To make this concrete, we derive the first few steps explicitly. From the definition $\hat{x}_0 = \hat{x}$ (multiplication by x), we have $\hat{x}_1 = \hat{\dot{x}} = b + 2\nu\nabla$, which matches (17). Now consider $\hat{x}_2 = \hat{\ddot{x}}$. Using the definition (25) with $m = 2$ and the Markov property, we can write

$$E(x(u)f(x(t), t)|x(s) = x) = \int dx_u x_u P(x_u, u|x, s) \left[\int dx_t f(x_t, t) P(x_t, t|x_u, u) \right].$$

The inner integral is a function $g(x_u, u) = E[f(x(t), t) \mid x(u) = x_u]$. Here and throughout this derivation we assume the temporal ordering $s < u < t$, consistent with the definition (25). The limits are taken as $t \downarrow u$ followed by $u \downarrow s$, so that the backward Kolmogorov equation applies for $u < t$ and the conditional expectation collapses smoothly as $u \rightarrow s$.

To compute the u -derivatives, it is convenient to introduce the time-extended backward generator²

$$D_u := \partial_u + \mathcal{L}_u, \quad \mathcal{L}_u = b(x, u) \cdot \nabla + \nu \Delta.$$

For sufficiently smooth $\phi(x, u)$ one has the backward identity

$$\frac{d}{du} E[\phi(x(u), u) \mid x(s) = x] = E[(D_u \phi)(x(u), u) \mid x(s) = x].$$

Iterating this identity gives

$$\frac{d^2}{du^2} E[\phi(x(u), u) \mid x(s) = x] = E[(D_u^2 \phi)(x(u), u) \mid x(s) = x].$$

Applying this with $\phi(x, u) = x g(x, u)$ and then taking the limits $t \downarrow u$ and $u \downarrow s$ yields

$$\hat{x}_2 f(x, s) = (D_s^2(xf))(x, s).$$

Expanding one power of D_s ,

$$\hat{x}_2 f = D_s(\hat{x}_1 f) - \hat{x}_1(D_s f),$$

so that

$$\hat{x}_2 = [D_s, \hat{x}_1].$$

Since $D_s = \partial_s + \mathcal{L}_s$ and $[\partial_s, \hat{x}_1] = \partial_s \hat{x}_1$, we obtain

$$\hat{x}_2 = [\mathcal{L}_s, \hat{x}_1] + \partial_s \hat{x}_1,$$

which agrees with (24) for general ν and is precisely the $m = 2$ case of the recursion formula.

In order to prove this equivalence, it's necessary to use the fact that the drift b is irrotational in generalized stochastic mechanics as follows from (10). A similar argument for general m gives

$$\hat{x}_{m+1} = [\mathcal{L}_s, \hat{x}_m] + \partial_s \hat{x}_m,$$

² Although $u > s$, this identity is termed the *backward* Kolmogorov equation because the generator \mathcal{L}_u acts on the test function rather than on the transition density. The forward (Fokker–Planck) equation instead involves the adjoint generator acting on $P(x_u, u \mid x, s)$.

which is (26).

Remark (ordering convention induced by the backward limit). Because the operators $\hat{x}(t)$ are constructed from conditional expectations using the backward-time limiting procedure $t \downarrow u \downarrow s$ in (25), the correspondence between a classical product and the associated operator insertion is *order-reversing*. Equivalently, for a monomial of time-labeled observables, the stochastic product corresponds naturally to a reverse-time-ordered operator product, which we denote by $\overline{\mathcal{T}}$.

Polynomial nature and analyticity: An immediate consequence of the recursion (26) is that each \hat{x}_m is an operator-valued polynomial of degree m in the diffusion constant ν . This can be proved by induction: \hat{x}_0 is independent of ν , and each application of the recursion introduces at most one additional factor of ν (through the generator $\mathcal{L}_s = b + \nu \nabla^2$). Therefore, for any fixed x and smooth test functions, the map $\nu \mapsto \hat{x}_m$ is an entire analytic function of the complex variable ν .

Moreover, the operators at different times can be reconstructed via a Taylor expansion around the reference time s . Using the Heisenberg-like evolution generated by the recursion, one finds

$$\hat{x}(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \hat{x}_m \frac{(t-s)^m}{m!}. \quad (27)$$

This series converges uniformly on bounded time intervals under mild regularity conditions on the drift and potential. Consequently, for any time-ordered product of such operators, the expectation

$$(1, T \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i) 1)_s = \sum_{m_1, \dots, m_n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(t_1-s)^{m_1} \cdots (t_n-s)^{m_n}}{m_1! \cdots m_n!} (1, \hat{x}_{m_1} \cdots \hat{x}_{m_n} 1)_s \quad (28)$$

is an analytic function of ν (as a uniform limit of polynomials) whenever the series converges absolutely.

Multi-time correlations via operator products: For real $\nu > 0$, we have the fundamental identity connecting operator expectations in the weighted Hilbert space to classical stochastic expectations:

$$(1, T \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i) 1)_s = E \left(\prod_{i=1}^n x(t_i) \right). \quad (29)$$

This follows from the construction of the operators $\hat{x}(t)$ as conditional expectations and the Markov property. The left-hand side involves the time-ordered product of Heisenberg-like

operators acting on the constant function 1 in \mathcal{H}_s , while the right-hand side is the classical multi-time correlation of the stochastic process.

The significance of (29) is twofold: First, it shows that the stochastic process encodes the same information as a non-commuting operator algebra when ν is real. Second, because the left-hand side is analytic in ν (as argued above) and the right-hand side is also analytic (by Lemma 2 in Section 6), the equality can be analytically continued to complex values of ν . In particular, for the specific imaginary value $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ that yields the Heisenberg commutation relations, we obtain

$$\left(1, T \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i; \nu) 1\right)_s \Big|_{\nu=\nu_C} = \mathbb{E}_\nu \left[\prod_{i=1}^n x(t_i) \right] \Big|_{\nu=\nu_C}. \quad (30)$$

That is, the operator expectation and the stochastic multi-time moment agree when the diffusion constant is set to $\nu = \nu_C$.

The left-hand side, after applying the similarity transformation (20) to convert from \mathcal{H}_s to the standard Hilbert space $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n, d^n x)$, becomes precisely the quantum mechanical time-ordered correlation $\langle \psi | T \prod \hat{x}(t_i) | \psi \rangle$. The right-hand side is the stochastic expectation of the complex process $z(t)$ defined by (14). This establishes the equivalence of multi-time correlations and provides the rigorous foundation for resolving Nelson's separability problem.

V. ANALYTIC CONTINUATION OF MULTI-TIME EXPECTATIONS

The key to restoring dynamical separability is the equality of stochastic and quantum multi-time correlations for ν_c . We prove this by analytic continuation in ν .

For a given complex ν with $\Re(\nu) > 0$ we have three objects:

- (a) The stochastic expectation

$$G_n(\nu; t_1, \dots, t_n) := \mathbb{E} \left[\prod_{i=1}^n x(t_i) \right], \quad (31)$$

where $x(t)$ solves the SDE (9) with diffusion constant ν .

- (b) The operator expectation in the weighted Hilbert space

$$F_n(\nu; t_1, \dots, t_n) := \left(1, \overline{\mathcal{T}} \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i; \nu) 1\right)_s, \quad (32)$$

with $\hat{x}(t; \nu)$ the Heisenberg-pictures operators constructed via the recursion (26) and T denoting time ordering.

- (c) The quantum mechanical expectation at $\nu = \nu_c$. At the distinguished value $\nu = \nu_c = -i\hbar/2m$, the similarity transformation W_s maps the stochastic velocity/momentum operators to the standard Schrödinger representation (Sec. IV A), and hence the time-ordered operator product constructed from the stochastic process coincides with the usual Heisenberg time-ordered product. Accordingly, we define the quantum correlation only at $\nu = \nu_c$ by

$$Q_n(t_1, \dots, t_n) := \langle \psi | \overline{T} \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i) | \psi \rangle. \quad (33)$$

where $\hat{x}(t)$ are the standard Heisenberg position operators for the Schrödinger Hamiltonian with wave function ψ as initial state.

Lemma V.1 (Equality for real ν). *For all real $\nu > 0$ and any fixed times,*

$$F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu). \quad (34)$$

Proof. For real ν , $x(t)$ is real-valued and the operator $\hat{x}(t; \nu)$ satisfies $(\phi, \hat{x}(t)\psi)_s = \mathbb{E}[\phi^*(x(s), s)x(t)\psi(x(s), s)]$. Setting $\phi = \psi = 1$ gives the result. \square

Lemma V.2 (Analyticity and continuation to ν_c). *Let $\nu_c = -i\hbar/(2m)$. Under the regularity assumptions stated in Appendix A, the following hold:*

1. *The stochastic multi-time moment*

$$G_n(\nu; t_1, \dots, t_n) = \mathbb{E} \left[\prod_{k=1}^n x(t_k) \right]$$

is holomorphic in ν on the half-plane $\Re(\nu) > 0$.

2. *The operator expectation*

$$F_n(\nu; t_1, \dots, t_n) = (1, T \prod_{k=1}^n \hat{x}(t_k; \nu) 1)_s$$

is holomorphic in a neighborhood U of ν_c .

3. Since $F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu)$ for all real $\nu > 0$, the identity theorem implies

$$F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu) \quad \text{for all } \nu \in U \cap \{\Re(\nu) > 0\}.$$

4. Consequently, G_n admits an analytic continuation to ν_c and

$$G_n(\nu_c) = F_n(\nu_c).$$

Lemma V.3 (Identification with the quantum representation at $\nu = \nu_c$). *Let $\nu = \nu_c = -i\hbar/2m$ and let $W_s : \mathcal{H}_s \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ be the map*

$$(W_s f)(x) = \psi(x, s) f(x, s),$$

defined in Eq. (20). Then:

(i) $W_s \hat{x}_j W_s^{-1}$ is multiplication by x_j on $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$.

(ii) If $\hat{v}_j(\nu_c) = b_j(x, s; \nu_c) + 2\nu_c \partial_j$ is the stochastic velocity operator on \mathcal{H}_s , then

$$W_s \hat{v}_j(\nu_c) W_s^{-1} = -\frac{i\hbar}{m} \partial_j \quad \text{on } L^2(\mathbb{R}^n),$$

and hence $W_s \hat{p}_j(\nu_c) W_s^{-1} = -i\hbar \partial_j$ for $\hat{p}_j = m\hat{v}_j$.

(iii) Consequently, for any time-ordered product of Heisenberg-picture position operators built from the stochastic operator dynamics at $\nu = \nu_c$,

$$F_n(\nu_c; t_1, \dots, t_n) = \left(1, T \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i; \nu_c) 1\right)_s = \langle \psi | T \prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_i) | \psi \rangle =: Q_n(t_1, \dots, t_n), \quad (35)$$

where $\hat{x}(t)$ on the right-hand side are the standard quantum Heisenberg position operators.

Proof. Items (i) and (ii) are the explicit intertwining relations computed in Sec. IV A: the multiplication operator \hat{x}_j is unchanged by W_s , and at $\nu = \nu_c$ the drift satisfies $b_j(x, s; \nu_c) = -i(\hbar/m)\partial_j \ln \psi(x, s)$, which cancels the corresponding term produced by conjugating ∂_j , yielding $W_s \hat{v}_j(\nu_c) W_s^{-1} = -(i\hbar/m)\partial_j$.

For (iii), the relations in (i)–(ii) show that at $\nu = \nu_c$ the basic canonical pair $(\hat{x}_j(\nu_c), \hat{p}_j(\nu_c))$ on \mathcal{H}_s is carried by W_s to the standard Schrödinger representation $(x_j, -i\hbar\partial_j)$ on $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Since the operator dynamics at $\nu = \nu_c$ coincide with the usual Heisenberg dynamics (for the same Hamiltonian and initial wave function), conjugation by W_s carries $\hat{x}(t; \nu_c)$ to the standard $\hat{x}(t)$ for all t . Therefore conjugation transports the time-ordered product, and because $(1, A 1)_s = \langle \psi | W_s A W_s^{-1} | \psi \rangle$, we obtain Eq. (35). \square

Theorem V.4 (Equivalence of correlations). *For $\nu_c = -i\hbar/2m$,*

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\prod_{i=1}^n z(t_i)\right] = \left\langle \psi \left| \overline{\mathcal{T}} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n \hat{x}(t_{n+1-i}) \right) \right| \psi \right\rangle, \quad (36)$$

where $z(t)$ solves the complex SDE (14) and $\hat{x}(t)$ are the standard Heisenberg operators.

Proof. By Lemma V.1 we have $F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu)$ for all real $\nu \in (0, \nu_0)$. By Lemma V.2 (with U as specified above), both F_n and G_n are holomorphic on U . Hence the identity theorem implies $F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu)$ for all $\nu \in U$, and in particular at $\nu = \nu_c$:

$$F_n(\nu_c) = G_n(\nu_c).$$

At $\nu = \nu_c$, the similarity transformation W_s identifies the stochastic operator algebra with the standard Schrödinger/Heisenberg representation (Sec. IV A). Therefore $F_n(\nu_c)$ equals the quantum mechanical time-ordered correlation $Q_n(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ defined in (33). Since $G_n(\nu_c) = \mathbb{E}[\prod_i z(t_i)]$, this yields (36). \square

Corollary V.5 (Dynamical separability). *For two non-interacting systems with $H = H_1 \otimes \mathbb{I} + \mathbb{I} \otimes H_2$, the multi-time stochastic correlations of any observable of system 1 are independent of H_2 .*

Proof. By Theorem V.4, the stochastic correlation equals the quantum correlation, which is dynamically separable. \square

VI. EXPLICIT EXAMPLE: NELSON'S COUNTEREXAMPLE REVISITED

We now apply Theorem V.4 to Nelson's original example. For the entangled state (4), the quantum autocorrelation (7) is $2 - it/\sqrt{2}$, independent of ω . Theorem V.4 guarantees that for $\nu_c = -i\hbar/2m$ (in Nelson's units $\nu_c = -i/\sqrt{2}$) the complex stochastic autocorrelation satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[z_1(t)z_1(0)] = \langle x_1(0)x_1(t) \rangle = 2 - it/\sqrt{2}. \quad (37)$$

Thus the ω dependence present in the real SM result (6) is absent for the complex diffusion. Dynamical separability is restored.

The equality (37) was obtained using the analytic continuation argument of Theorem V.4. In the next section we verify the same result directly from the complex stochastic differential equation, without invoking analytic continuation, thereby providing an independent consistency check of the formal argument.

VII. DIRECT STOCHASTIC COMPUTATION OF THE MULTI-TIME EXPECTATION

We now confirm Eq. (37) directly from the complex stochastic dynamics. Unlike Section VI, which relied on analytic continuation of multi-time expectations, the argument here proceeds entirely from the stochastic differential equation (38) and the associated Gaussian moment structure. The computation also makes explicit how the two-particle entangled system evolves and why the oscillator frequency ω cancels from the autocorrelation of particle 1.

1. Complex SDE and Rosenbrock coordinates

In Nelson's units ($m = 1$, $\hbar = \sqrt{2}$), the complex diffusion satisfies

$$dz(t) = -i\hbar \nabla_z \ln \psi(z(t), t) dt + \sqrt{-i\hbar} dW(t), \quad (38)$$

where $W(t)$ is a standard \mathbb{R}^2 Brownian motion.

Write $z = x + iy$ with $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and introduce the rotated coordinates (Appendix B, Eq. (B.1))

$$X = x + y, \quad Y = x - y. \quad (39)$$

As shown in Appendix B (Eqs. (B.2)–(B.3)), the SDE becomes

$$dX(t) = (B_R(X, Y, t) + B_I(X, Y, t)) dt, \quad (40)$$

$$dY(t) = (B_R(X, Y, t) - B_I(X, Y, t)) dt + \sqrt{\hbar} dW(t). \quad (41)$$

Thus X evolves deterministically given Y , while diffusion occurs only in the Y -variables. The forward Fokker–Planck equation therefore takes the form (cf. Appendix B, Eq. (B.4))

$$\partial_t \rho = -\nabla_X \cdot (\rho \beta_X) - \nabla_Y \cdot (\rho \beta_Y) + \frac{\hbar}{2} \Delta_Y \rho, \quad (42)$$

where

$$\beta_X = B_R + B_I, \quad \beta_Y = B_R - B_I. \quad (43)$$

2. Gaussian preservation and two-particle structure

For the quadratic Hamiltonian (3) and entangled Gaussian initial state (4), Schrödinger evolution preserves Gaussianity (Gaussian state evolution theorem). Thus

$$\psi(z, t) = N(t) \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}z^\top K(t)z\right), \quad (44)$$

where $K(t)$ is a complex symmetric 2×2 matrix.

Hence

$$\nabla_z \ln \psi(z, t) = -K(t)z, \quad (45)$$

and the stochastic equation becomes

$$dz(t) = A(t)z(t) dt + \sqrt{-i\hbar} dW(t), \quad A(t) = i\hbar K(t). \quad (46)$$

Because the drift is linear and the noise additive Gaussian, the joint law of $(X(t), Y(t))$ remains Gaussian for all t .

3. Riccati reduction

Inserting the Gaussian ansatz into Schrödinger's equation yields

$$\dot{K} = -\frac{2i}{\hbar}K^2 + \frac{i}{\hbar}V, \quad V = \text{diag}(0, \omega^2). \quad (47)$$

Linearizing via $K = PQ^{-1}$ gives

$$\dot{Q} = i\hbar P, \quad (48)$$

$$\dot{P} = \frac{i}{\hbar}VQ, \quad (49)$$

with initial data

$$Q(0) = I, \quad P(0) = K(0), \quad (50)$$

where

$$K(0) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (51)$$

Eliminating P yields

$$\ddot{Q} = -VQ, \quad Q(0) = I, \quad \dot{Q}(0) = i\hbar K(0). \quad (52)$$

4. Two-particle cross-moment evolution

Define

$$m(t) = \mathbb{E}[z(t) z_1(0)] = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{E}[z_1(t) z_1(0)] \\ \mathbb{E}[z_2(t) z_1(0)] \end{pmatrix}. \quad (53)$$

From (46),

$$\dot{m}(t) = A(t)m(t). \quad (54)$$

Because $z(0) = x(0)$ is real with covariance (5),

$$m(0) = \begin{pmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (55)$$

Since $A(t) = \dot{Q}(t)Q(t)^{-1}$,

$$m(t) = Q(t)m(0). \quad (56)$$

Solving (52) gives

$$Q(t) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t & -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t \\ -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}\omega} \sin(\omega t) & \cos(\omega t) + \frac{i\sqrt{2}}{\omega} \sin(\omega t) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (57)$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}[z_1(t)z_1(0)] = \left(1 + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t\right) 2 - \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t = 2 + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t. \quad (58)$$

The ω -dependence cancels identically, demonstrating that the stochastic evolution of particle 1 is independent of the distant oscillator dynamics.

From Eq. (7) we recall that

$$\langle x_1(t)x_1(0) \rangle = 2 - \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t, \quad \langle x_1(0)x_1(t) \rangle = 2 + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}t. \quad (59)$$

Thus the stochastic expectation $\mathbb{E}[z_1(t)z_1(0)]$ corresponds to the reverse time operator ordering. When placed inside the reverse-time-ordering operation appearing in Theorem V.4, this yields precisely the quantum correlation (37).

This direct computation therefore agrees exactly with the analytic-continuation result of Section VI and provides an explicit demonstration that dynamical separability is restored for Nelson's example. It also provides supporting evidence for the validity of theorem V.4.

VII. DISCUSSION

We have shown that Nelson's dynamical separability problem is resolved by choosing the imaginary diffusion constant $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ in generalized stochastic mechanics. For this value, the stochastic operator algebra becomes isomorphic to the Heisenberg algebra, and analytic continuation proves that multi-time stochastic correlations equal quantum mechanical ones. The explicit verification in Nelson's counterexample confirms that the ω dependence disappears.

Several open questions remain, including a deeper physical understanding of why the imaginary diffusion constant eliminates the coupling, the resolution of Wallstrom's objection concerning multi-valued phases [25–28], and the possible connections discussed in the next section.

VIII. SPECULATIVE OUTLOOK

After these formal mathematical pages, allow me to indulge in some conjecturing about the implications of this theory.

A. Interpretation and a conjecture about a possible chaotic attractor

Resolving the multi-time dilemma with an imaginary diffusion constant forces a reinterpretation of the underlying stochastic process. Instead of a real Brownian motion in real space, the process must unfold in **complex space**. The particle's position at any time is a complex number, $z(t) = x(t) + iy(t)$. Quantum measurements correspond to observations on the real axis ($y = 0$), where the probability density $\rho(x, 0, t)$ is equal to $|\psi(x, t)|^2$. This offers a compelling picture: unobserved quantum reality is a stochastic process in a complex domain, and the familiar rules of quantum mechanics describe the intersection of this process with our real-valued world. As Rosenbrock showed (see Appendix B), the Born rule applies precisely at the *crossing points* where the trajectory intersects the real axis, providing a natural explanation for why quantum probabilities emerge from the complex dynamics.

This leads to further speculation. The probability distribution $\rho(x, y, t)$ in the full complex plane evolves according to a well-behaved Fokker-Planck equation. It is conceivable that this distribution is the invariant measure of an underlying deterministic, but **chaotic**,

dynamical system. The trajectory $z(t)$ might represent motion on a strange attractor within a complex phase space. The stochastic term in the SDE would then represent not fundamental randomness, but the effective behavior of this intricate chaotic motion. The fact that the real axis acts as an attractor (as implied by the preservation of the Born probability near $y = 0$) supports this conjecture.

B. Possible relevance of the Lorentz-Dirac equation and radiation

The Lorentz-Dirac equation describes a classical point charge's motion, including the reactive force from its own radiation. It is famous for its problematic solutions, such as "runaway" acceleration and/or "pre-acceleration" that violates causality. Nelson wondered if the stochastic motion in his theory was a manifestation of chaotic behavior from classical electrodynamics [5] (in List of Open Problems, pg 133). The stochastic process in complex spacetime could emerge from a more fundamental, deterministic chaotic process, perhaps related to the self-interaction of charged particles.

It has already been demonstrated that the Lorentz-Dirac equation when analytically continued into complex spacetime has simple oscillatory solutions possibly replacing the runaway solutions in real spacetime [29]. Preliminary simulations run with chatgpt of small deviations from these oscillatory solutions have resulted in positive Lyapunov coefficients for some values of the equation's parameters suggesting the possible onset of chaos. One needs to consider ensembles of trajectories, as in Hamilton-Jacobi theory, to contemplate this as a stochastic origin of quantum mechanics, at least for charged particles. It is too early to say if this could be the origin of quantum indeterminacy. Rosenbrock [14] has shown that the stochastic trajectories in complex space are attracted by the drift term back to the real axis in his theory, so that the probability of the particle being found near to the real axis does not reduce over time. This suggests that the real axis is acting as an attractor, and perhaps a chaotic one. I speculate that the Lorentz-Dirac equation in complex spacetime might have this property.

There is a purely electromagnetic particle model, or rather a class of them, that rely on complex spacetime, and that could be used as models for the diffusing particles in this theory [30]. These semiclassical models include spin and magnetic moments with g factors of 2, the same as the Dirac equation for relativistic quantum mechanics. There are several other

strange facts relating electromagnetism and quantum theory that I have long pondered. If one considers the free-particle Schrödinger equation, and treats the probability current and density as if they were a classical charged current and density, and one then calculates the radiation that would be emitted, it is found to be zero for all multipole orders [31]. This is quite surprising considering the potentially extremely violent temporal undulations that can occur in a linear superposition of waves in Schrödinger's equation even for a free particle. It does not radiate at any multipolar order. I think that this fact might be an important clue to the nature and origins of quantum mechanics. Another curious result is a derivation of the stationary state Schrödinger equation from the classical self-force equation of a particle in a thermal bath [32]. Nelson pointed out that the fine structure constant $\alpha = e^2/\hbar c$ relates Planck's constant to two electromagnetic constants e and c . This suggested to him that the origins of quantum mechanics are possibly electromagnetic. This idea has been pursued most vigorously by stochastic electrodynamics advocates [33].

An interesting alternative to the Lorentz-Dirac equation as a source of possible chaos is based on Stueckelberg-Horwitz-Piron (SHP) theory of relativistic mechanics based on a Lorentz invariant world time variation of electromagnetism [34, 35]. These authors have shown that these nonlinear trajectory equations have strange attractors and chaos. They considered motions restricted to real spacetime only. Their theory, when analytically continued to complex spacetime, also has zitterbewegung-like solutions like the Lorentz-Dirac equation does, and is likely to have chaotic behavior when small deviations from these solutions are studied. It is conceivable that it could have multiple mass values which correspond to chaotic attractors.

C. Comments on Bell's theorem and other no-go theorems regarding stochastic mechanics

Feynman and Nelson both argued and asserted that if one has a model that reproduces the positions of particles then this is enough [22]. So the full measurement theory of Von Neumann is denied and no-go theorems based on his axioms are not effective in ruling out stochastic mechanics or Bohmian mechanics. Bell's theorem, on the other hand, is not avoided by this assertion. Nelson points out that Bell's theorem is less of a problem than the lack of dynamic separability. But the stochastic theory, even with imaginary

diffusion constant, is still nonlocal in the exact same way as ordinary quantum mechanics. If superdeterminism applies to the whole universe, as 't Hooft proposes [36], then the stochastic model can be local, at least when applying it to the whole universe. When considering subsystems of the whole universe, in a superdeterministic worldview, they would appear to be nonlocally linked as the underlying determinism is not apparent to local observers.

D. Comments on non-Markovian processes and the connection to Barandes' indivisible stochastic framework

Nelson himself suggested that the separability problem might be solved by moving to a non-Markovian process [5] §23. This intuition has been borne out in subsequent work; more recently, Barandes has developed a comprehensive framework of *indivisible stochastic processes* [37–39], which are a far-reaching generalization of non-Markovian dynamics. In this framework, the future behavior of a system is not determined solely by its present state, nor even by a finite memory of the past, but rather by a fundamentally indivisible temporal structure that cannot be decomposed into a sequence of independent steps.

Our complex diffusion model with $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ provides a concrete realization of a non-Markovian stochastic model of quantum mechanics. As shown in Section 4, the transformation to coordinates $X = x + y$ and $Y = x - y$ reveals that the X component evolves deterministically and can be eliminated, leaving a non-Markovian equation for Y alone [13, 14]. Explicitly, from (32) and (33) we have

$$X(t) = \int_0^t (B_R(X(t), Y(t), t) + B_I(X(t), Y(t), t)) dt + X(0),$$

and substituting this expression into the SDE for Y yields

$$dY(t) = (B_R(X(t), Y(t), t) - B_I(X(t), Y(t), t)) dt + \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{m}} dw(t),$$

where the drift at time t depends on the entire past history of Y through $X(t)$. Thus the reduced dynamics for Y is non-Markovian, and in fact falls under the broader class of indivisible processes identified by Barandes.

This connection is significant for several reasons. First, it shows that the complex diffusion model, while Markovian in the full (X, Y) space, gives rise to an effective dynamics for the physical coordinate $x = (X + Y)/2$ that is genuinely non-Markovian when expressed solely

in terms of x . Second, it provides a concrete example of how a non-Markovian stochastic process can replicate quantum correlations exactly, thereby addressing Nelson's original concern. Third, it situates our work within a developing research program that aims to reconstruct quantum theory from stochastic first principles [39], although it's not obvious that complex stochastic mechanics can be cast in the form of an indivisible stochastic process.

E. Dark matter may be ordinary matter, or anti-matter which has been displaced from the real axes by an unknown mechanism

If we can only detect matter that is very near to the real axes, then maybe there is matter that has been displaced from the real axis that nevertheless can produce a gravitational effect on the real axis that we can observe, but that has no other form of interaction. Perhaps this could account for some or all of the dark matter. In fact, perhaps this could be where the missing antimatter is hiding. It is prevented from annihilating ordinary matter by being displaced in the imaginary direction. It could also be where the other chirality particles are hiding too. There could quite literally be parallel universes embedded in complex space time.

IX. CONCLUSION

We have shown that Nelson's dynamical separability problem is resolved by choosing the imaginary diffusion constant $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ in generalized stochastic mechanics. For this value, the multi-time stochastic correlations analytically continue to the quantum mechanical correlations, and the operator algebra becomes isomorphic to the Heisenberg algebra. We verified this explicitly by showing that in Nelson's original counterexample, Theorem V.4 guarantees that the complex diffusion process yields the quantum mechanical autocorrelation, which is independent of ω . The principal obstacle to stochastic mechanics as a viable interpretation of quantum theory is thus removed.

Many open questions remain, including experimental constraints on the diffusion parameter, a full resolution of Wallstrom's objection, a deeper physical understanding of why the imaginary diffusion constant eliminates the coupling, and the speculative connections to chaos, electromagnetism, and non-Markovian dynamics outlined above. The emerging

framework of indivisible stochastic processes due to Barandes offers a promising context in which to pursue these questions further. Rosenbrock’s insight that the Born rule applies at the crossing points where trajectories meet the real axis provides a compelling physical picture that unifies these ideas (see Appendix B). Nelson’s ardent dream of a stochastic foundation for quantum mechanics is now more feasible than ever.

AI DISCLOSURE

Certain intermediate steps in the proofs of this paper were cross-checked using [DEEPSEEK with DEEPTHINK] and with [OPEN AI Math Proof] to ensure algebraic consistency. The AIs were used to verify the analytic continuation from the stochastic expectation to the quantum expectation. The author has manually audited these steps and takes full responsibility for the correctness of the final proof.

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Appendix A: Proof of Lemma V.2 via the Rosenbrock formulation

In this appendix we prove Lemma V.2 using the real (X, Y) representation of the complex diffusion. The argument establishes analyticity of the multi-time stochastic expectations for $\Re(\nu) > 0$ and their analytic continuation to the boundary value

$$\nu_c = -\frac{i\hbar}{2m}.$$

1. A.1 Real formulation of the complex diffusion

Let $z = x + iy$. Following Rosenbrock, introduce the rotated real variables

$$X = x + y, \quad Y = x - y.$$

Write the complex diffusion constant as

$$\nu = \alpha - i\beta, \quad \alpha = \Re(\nu).$$

In these variables the stochastic differential equation becomes

$$dX_t = \beta_X(X_t, Y_t, t; \nu) dt, \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$dY_t = \beta_Y(X_t, Y_t, t; \nu) dt + \sqrt{2\alpha} dW_t, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where W_t is standard real Brownian motion.

The generator takes the form

$$L_\nu = \beta_X \partial_X + \beta_Y \partial_Y + \alpha \Delta_Y.$$

Thus diffusion acts only in the Y directions, with diffusion coefficient proportional to $\Re(\nu)$.

2. A.2 Well-posedness for $\Re(\nu) > 0$

Assume:

1. For each fixed (X, Y, t) , the drift coefficients β_X and β_Y are holomorphic in ν in a neighborhood U of ν_c .
2. They are locally Lipschitz in (X, Y) , uniformly for $\nu \in U$.
3. They satisfy uniform linear growth bounds on U .
4. The initial data has finite moments of all orders.

If $\alpha = \Re(\nu) > 0$, then L_ν is degenerate parabolic: elliptic in the Y variables and first-order in X . Under the above assumptions the SDE admits a unique strong solution, and standard Grönwall estimates give uniform moment bounds on finite time intervals.

3. A.3 Holomorphic dependence on ν

Fix times t_1, \dots, t_n . We show that

$$G_n(\nu) = \mathbb{E} \left[\prod_{k=1}^n x(t_k) \right]$$

is holomorphic in ν for $\Re(\nu) > 0$.

Construct the solution by Picard iteration:

$$(X^{(k+1)}, Y^{(k+1)}) = \Phi_\nu(X^{(k)}, Y^{(k)}),$$

where Φ_ν denotes the integral form of the SDE.

Because the drift coefficients are holomorphic in ν and locally Lipschitz in (X, Y) , each Picard iterate is holomorphic in ν . Uniform convergence on compact subsets of $U \cap \{\Re(\nu) > 0\}$ implies that the solution (X_t, Y_t) depends holomorphically on ν in this region.

Since the coordinate transformation $x = (X + Y)/2$ is linear, the multi-time moment $G_n(\nu)$ is holomorphic for $\Re(\nu) > 0$.

4. A.4 Analytic continuation to ν_c

As $\alpha \downarrow 0$,

$$L_\nu \longrightarrow L_{\nu_c} = \beta_X \partial_X + \beta_Y \partial_Y,$$

a first-order operator.

The coefficients remain smooth in ν , and no singularity occurs in the parameter dependence. Thus L_ν forms an analytic family of operators in a neighborhood U of ν_c .

The operator expectation

$$F_n(\nu) = (1, T \prod_{k=1}^n \hat{x}(t_k; \nu) 1)_s$$

is holomorphic in U by the polynomial dependence of the recursion coefficients on ν .

Since

$$F_n(\nu) = G_n(\nu) \quad \text{for all real } \nu > 0,$$

and both sides are holomorphic on the connected set $U \cap \{\Re(\nu) > 0\}$, the identity theorem implies equality throughout this region.

Therefore the analytic continuation of $G_n(\nu)$ to ν_c exists and satisfies

$$G_n(\nu_c) = F_n(\nu_c).$$

By Lemma V.3, $F_n(\nu_c)$ equals the standard quantum time-ordered correlation, which completes the proof of Lemma V.2.

Appendix B: Rosenbrock's analysis of complex diffusion and the physical interpretation of quantum phenomena

Rosenbrock [13–15] provided a detailed analysis of the complex diffusion process with $\nu = -i\hbar/2m$ that reveals profound connections to quantum mechanics. His work is essential for understanding the physical interpretation of the formalism.

1. The deterministic X coordinate and the Fokker-Planck equation

Starting from the one-dimensional SDE (14) with $z = x + iy$, Rosenbrock introduced the rotated coordinates

$$X = x + y, \quad Y = x - y. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

In these coordinates, the SDE decomposes as

$$dX(t) = (B_R(X, Y, t) + B_I(X, Y, t))dt, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$dY(t) = (B_R(X, Y, t) - B_I(X, Y, t))dt + \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{m}}dw(t), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where B_R and B_I are the real and imaginary parts of the drift expressed in terms of X and Y . Crucially, the equation for X contains *no diffusion term*; X evolves deterministically given the path of Y .

The Fokker-Planck equation for the joint probability density $\rho(x, y, t)$ takes the form

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho b_R) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\rho b_I) - \frac{\hbar}{8m} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right)^2 \rho = 0, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

subject to the boundary condition on the real axis

$$\rho(x, 0, t) = e^{2R(x,t)} = |\psi(x, t)|^2. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

2. The Born rule at crossing points

Rosenbrock's most significant insight concerns the interpretation of measurements. Physical measurements, he argued, only register the particle when its trajectory *crosses the real axis* ($y = 0$). At these crossing points, the probability density is given by $|\psi(x, t)|^2$. This is not an assumption but a consequence of the dynamics: the Fokker-Planck equation (B.4)

together with the boundary condition (B.5) ensures that the density on the real axis evolves according to the Born rule at all times.

This provides a natural explanation for several quantum phenomena:

a. Destructive interference

In regions where the wave function vanishes due to destructive interference, $|\psi|^2 \approx 0$. According to Rosenbrock's interpretation, particles in such regions might have trajectories with large imaginary components, so they rarely cross the real axis there. Consequently, detectors placed in these regions register few events. The interference pattern emerges from the statistics of crossing points. As an analogy, consider a large school of dolphins swimming on the open ocean observed from the air. At any instant there will be a fraction visible on the surface as they breath air and another fraction underwater looking for food or playing around. There could be regions on the surface where there are no dolphins visible because they were passing over of a school of fish. This looks like destructive interference from the air.

b. Quantum tunneling

Tunneling through a potential barrier can be understood as the particle taking a path in the complex plane that goes *under* the barrier. In regions where the potential energy exceeds the particle's energy, the classical momentum becomes imaginary, allowing the trajectory to circumvent the barrier by acquiring an imaginary component. When the trajectory later returns to the real axis on the other side of the barrier, a detection event can occur. The tunneling probability is determined by the likelihood of such complex paths, which is encoded in the wave function.

c. The real axis as a strange attractor

The preservation of the Born probability on the real axis implies that trajectories are constantly being drawn back toward $y = 0$. The density $\rho(x, 0, t)$ remains equal to $|\psi|^2$ for all t , meaning that the probability of finding the particle arbitrarily far from the real

axis does not accumulate; there is a constant "flow" back to the real axis. This behavior is characteristic of a *strange attractor*: the real axis acts as an attracting set for the complex dynamics, even though individual trajectories may wander into the complex plane.

Rosenbrock's analysis thus provides a physically intuitive picture: quantum particles follow continuous paths in complex space, but measurements only detect them when they intersect the real axis. All quantum phenomena—interference, tunneling, probability conservation—emerge naturally from this underlying stochastic process. This interpretation complements the rigorous analytic continuation proof in the main text and offers a compelling vision of quantum mechanics as emerging from a complex classical dynamics.

3. Connection to chaos and attractors

The idea that the real axis acts as an attractor suggests a deeper connection to chaos theory. If the underlying deterministic dynamics (before the addition of noise) possesses a strange attractor in the complex plane, the stochastic term could represent the effective noise arising from chaotic fluctuations. Rosenbrock's result that the crossing-point density remains $|\psi|^2$ would then be a manifestation of the invariant measure of this chaotic attractor projected onto the real axis.

This speculation aligns with Nelson's own conjecture that stochastic mechanics might ultimately be derivable from a chaotic classical electrodynamics [5]. The Lorentz-Dirac equation in complex spacetime [29] and the Stueckelberg-Horwitz-Piron theory [34, 35] provide concrete candidates for such underlying deterministic dynamics.

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